

THE ROLE OF THE EDUCATIONIST IN CONSERVING AND SUSTAINING THE BLUE-ECONOMY IN NIGERIA

Mabel Obioma Ajah
Institute of Education,
University of Calabar, Calabar, Nigeria
Email: obimb68@gmail.com

Abstract

The Africa's Blue/ocean economy is three times the size of its landmass and a major contributor to continental transformation and growth through knowledge of marine and aquatic biotechnology, the development of seas, rivers and lakes, transports and fishing, the growth of an Africa-wild shipping industry, and exploitations and beneficiation of deep sea mineral and other resources. The world at the moment is driving towards maximum but sustainable utilization of the marine environment so as to meet its numerous needs. This quest has subjected the "Blue Economy: the seas, rivers and lakes and their resources to undue pressures. The impact of industrialization, coastal development, deep sea oil exploration and exploitation, and climate change form additional pressures from the exploitation of marine fisheries resources. Besides that, the effect of pollution and anthropogenic activities emanating from both the several coastal and coastland, in particular, the activities of the Niger Delta Militants, the avengers and other oil pipe line vandals are becoming more and more complex. The role of the educationist is therefore inevitable and highly needed to train and re-train relevant human resources on how best to manage and conserve the blue economy, the seas and other aquatic environments with adequate knowledge of aquatic and pollution control measures. The need for effective monitoring and proactive responses to the dynamic nature of the Blue Economy is quite inevitable, as a panacea to saving it from total collapse.

Keywords: Blue economy, Biodiversity, Sustainability, Conservation, Educationist.

Introduction

The importance of the world oceans is not limited to a wide range of biodiversity and ecosystems but equally covers the food chains and climate change for the almost nine billion people (United Nations Educational Programme (UNEP) 2015). Since about three quarters of the earth's surface is the oceans and it is also habitat to more than one half of all life forms, thus, creating the false impression that they constitute unlimited resources. The tendency therefore is to greatly over-explore and degrade it far beyond the shores.

It is clear that issues relating to the oceans are integral part of most of the Sustainable Development Goals and the transition towards the inclusive green economy on which their success lies. The complimentary "blue" aspect of that transition which is regarded as the blue economy do offer an innovative approach to conserving the oceans as well as reap their benefits in a more equitable and sustainable manner (UNEP 2015). There is no gainsaying that without the adoption of a more sustainable management approach on the oceans, they, conversely, will not be able to

sustain the world population that depends on them (UNEP 2015). This calls for the role of the educationists through some planned advocacy programmes, basic researches, seminars and workshops to create awareness, to train and re-train, educate and properly inform the masses of the potentials that lie in the blue economy, the danger of its overexploitation and ways it could be conserved and sustainably managed since we are now aware that our marine and coastal environment is under pressure from both land based and ocean-based pollution sources.

It is true that the European Union (EU) legislation to protect the marine environment has been progressively implemented in many relevant areas such as the regulation of fisheries through the Common Fisheries Policy (CFP) or the control of input of nutrients and chemicals into the water through the Water Framework Directive (WFD), but these pieces of legislation, although crucial complementary tools to the protection of marine waters, do contribute to the protection of the sea only from specific pressures leading to a fragmented and sectorial approach. Consequently, the European Union has adopted two instruments, namely, the 2002 EU Recommendation on Integrated Coastal Zone Management and the 2008 Marine Strategy Framework Directive, which offer a comprehensive and integrated approach to the protection of all European coastal marine waters. This piece of information needs to be made known to the teeming population of the third world countries, Nigeria in particular who depends largely on water resources for their livelihood. The Marine Strategy Framework Directive (or Marine Directive) happens to be the first encompassing piece of EU legislation that is specific on the protection of the marine environment and natural resources and does create a framework for the sustainable use of our marine waters.

The role of the African Union (AU) in developing and implementing the Blue Economy policy and strategy within the African region cannot be overemphasized For over a

has built an enlarged Africa-wide consensus respect to very vital role of promoting structural transformation in African that the Blue Economy could play during the next decade encapsulated in the African Union's 2050 Africa's Integrated Maritime Strategy (AU 2050 AIMS), which describes the Blue Economy as the "new front of African Renaissance". Besides, the Blue Economy is at the centre of the AU's Agenda 2063 where it was unanimously declared "Africa's future" and recognized as a catalyst for socioeconomic transformation. Consequently, the African Union launched the African Day (July) and Decade of Seas and Ocean 2015-2024 to rally action on the Blue Economy (United Nations Economic Commission for Africa (UNECA) 2015).

Island and coastal development nations have been leading in this Blue Economy advocacy, being fully aware that the oceans play a key role in humanity's future and that the Blue Economy offers an approach to sustainable development better suited to the circumstances, constraints and challenges. Coincidentally, cutting edge technologies and rising commodity prices are opening up new realms of opportunity for submarine exploitation and there is urgent need for sound management of ocean resources for the realization of sustainable development. The marine coastal resource bases have been overburdened by the enormous human development activities therein. The Food and Agricultural Organisation (FAO, 2012) data shows that 87% of global fish stock are fully or over exploited. While loss of biodiversity, ecological function and the decline in provision of environmental services result from increasing pollution and unsustainable coastal development, climate change threatens to remove virtually the very foundations of vast swathes of coastal development.

In addition, rising atmospheric CO₂ levels through ocean acidification and changes in ocean chemistry, at a speed faster than at any time in the last 300 million years, do undermine the fundamental aspects of many marine ecosystems (IGBP IOC SCOR 2013).

Conversely, the ability of the oceans to meet sustainable development needs is enormous; but only if they can be maintained in and/or restored to a healthy and productive state. The importance of oceans for sustainable development has been recognized from the beginning of the United Nations Conference on Environment and Development (UNCED) process, in Agenda 21, the Johannesburg Plan of Implementation and reaffirmed in the outcome document of the Rio+20 Conference that took place in 2012 at Janciro, Brazil; but ongoing trends of exploitation and degradation of marine and coastal ecosystems show that endeavours to date have been insufficient and that more need to be and must be done (The Blue Economy Concept 2012).

In the light of the above assertions, this paper therefore x-rayed the concept of Blue Economy, Benefits and Opportunities of the Blue Economy, Sustainable use and conservation of biodiversity. It highlighted the different roles of the educationist and how to use the roles to enhance the conservation and sustainability of the blue economy. The paper ended by positing that educationist should be incorporated into any management team/programme that is established for proper utilization and sustainable development of the Blue Economy so as to harness his/her wealth of knowledge and for dissemination of the right information regarding the sustainable use of water resources for maximum benefit.

Blue planet/economy

Blue planet simply stands for the oceans of the world. The oceans which constitute more than 95% of the biosphere cover 72% of the surface of our blue planet. The oceans are the origin of life and continue to support all life today through the generation of oxygen, absorption of carbon dioxide, recycling of nutrients and regulation of global climate and temperature.

The oceans supply considerable portion of the world population with food and livelihoods and serve as the means of transport for 80% of global trade (United Nations Conference on

Trade and Development (UNCTAD) 2012). The marine and coastal environment equally comprise key resources for the important global tourism industry; supporting all aspects of the tourism development cycle from infrastructure and the familiar "sun, sand and sea" formula to the diverse and expanding domain of nature-based tourism. The seabed presently provides 32% of the global supply of hydrocarbons with exploration expanding. Advancing technologies are opening new frontiers of marine resource development from bio-prospecting to the mining of seabed mineral resources. Vast potential for renewable "blue energy" production from wind, wave, tidal, thermal and biomass sources are also gotten from the sea. The Blue Economy therefore, is a developing world initiative pioneered by Shift Development in Small Island States (SIDS).

It is relevant to all coastal states and countries with interest in waters beyond their national jurisdiction. The Blue Economy conceptualizes oceans as "Development Spaces" where spatial planning incorporates conservation, sustainable use, bioprospecting, oil and mineral wealth extraction, sustainable energy production and marine transport. Between 20th-22nd June 2012, The "Rio+ 20" United Nations Conference on Sustainable Development (UNCSD) took place in Rio de Janeiro, Japan, with one of the key themes on the further development and refinement of the institutional framework for sustainable Development and the second being the advancement of the "Green Economy" concept which was considered as an important and indispensable tool required for eradicating poverty (the greatest global challenge) and for sustainable development.

The outcome document of the conference, *emphasize that it should contribute to eradicating poverty as well as sustained economic growth, enhancing social inclusion, improving human welfare and creating opportunities for employment and decent work for all, while maintaining the healthy functioning of the Earth's ecosystems*. (Para 56. *The future we want, UNCSD 2012*). Prior to

the conference many coastal countries questioned the focus of the Green Economy and its applicability to them and this led to greater emphasis on the "Blue Economy" approach which has broad relevance as the Oceans, including humankind's common heritage of the High Seas, represent in many respects the ultimate frontier for humanity and its quest for sustainable development. Several attempts by Institutions were then made to expand the Blue aspect of the Green Economy as being an integral part of the "Green Economy as stated in a "Blue World" report¹. All through and during the Conference there was a growing appreciation that the world's Oceans and Seas need more in depth attention and coordinated action reflected in various initiatives inter alia the United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs (UNDESA) expert group meeting on the Oceans, the Seas and Sustainable Development, the work of the Global Ocean Commission, the Global Partnership for Oceans and the prominence given to oceans and seas in the UN five-year Action Agenda 2012-2016.

The Blue economy: a framework for sustainable development

The Blue Economy paradigm comprises a sustainable development framework for developing countries addressing equity in access to development and the sharing of benefits from marine resources; offering scope for re-investment in human development and the alleviation of crippling national debt burdens.

The Blue Economy adopts the same desired outcome as the Rio +20 Green Economy initiative such as: "improved human well-being and social equity, while significantly reducing environmental risks and ecological scarcities" (United Nations Environmental Programme (UNEP) 2013) and it endorses the same principles of low carbon, resource efficiency and social inclusion, but it is grounded in a developing world context and focusing on

the principle of equity ensuring that developing countries:

- Optimize the benefits received from the development of their marine environments e.g. fishery agreements, bioprospecting, oil and mineral extraction.
- Promote national equity, including gender equality, and in particular the generation of inclusive growth and decent jobs for all.
- Have their concerns and interests properly reflected in the development of seas beyond national jurisdiction; including the refinement of international governance mechanisms and their concerns as States close to seabed development.

The mainstreaming of fairness at international and national levels offers scope for developing countries to realize greater revenue from their resources and reinvest in their populace, environmental management, reduce national debt levels and add to the eradication of poverty and hunger. At the center of the Blue Economy concept is the de-coupling of socioeconomic development from environmental degradation. To achieve this, the Blue Economy approach is established upon the assessment and incorporation of the real value of the natural (blue) capital into all aspects of economic activity (conceptualization, planning, trade, travel, infrastructure development, renewable resource exploitation, energy production/consumption). Efficiency and optimization of resource use are paramount whilst respecting environmental and ecological parameters particularly where sustainable source and usage of local raw materials and utilizing are feasible.

The Blue Economy approach identifies and places renewed emphasis on the critical need for the international community to address effectively the sound management of resources in and beneath international waters by the further

responsibility to protect the high seas, which cover 64% of the surface of our oceans and constitute more than 90% of their volume.

Benefits and opportunities of the blue economy

It is a known fact that issues and problems bring with them challenges and opportunities and the Blue Economy offers a set of opportunities for sustainable, clean, equitable blue growth in both traditional and emerging sectors as follows but not limited to fisheries, tourism, food security, aquaculture, shipping and port facilities, energy supply, biotechnology, and submarine mining amongst others (GOC 2008; FAO 2010; UNWATO 2013; OECD 2012; IFFO 2013; PARM 2004; UNCTAD 2012; IEA 2010; IOC/UNESCO, IMO, FAO, UNDP, 2011).

The benefits of the Blue Economy likewise apply to SIDS and more often than not to coastal countries and in the end the Blue Economy approach offers the means for the sound utilization of resources beyond national jurisdiction, which include, the sustainable development of the common heritage of humanity and the resources of the High Seas.

The Blue Economy approach will set in place the policies, legislation, infrastructure and incentives to facilitate the transition to a low carbon economy utilizing all the tools at its disposal including the ocean's enormous potential for renewable energy (wind, wave, tidal, thermal and biomass) generation.

Sustainability and sustainable use of biodiversity

Sustainability is the ability to maintain productivity which is aimed at achieving economic development to secure higher standards of living now and in future, as well as seek to protect the environment in the process. A sustainable system leads to greater human utility, greater efficiency of resource use and a balance with the environment which is favourable to humans and most other species. (HOMSO, 1994)

Biodiversity has to do with different species of living organisms in connection with their nature, location, density, and the position they occupy or trophic level in food chain in the ecosystem. These living organisms and their non-living components are regarded as natural capital of many marine and coastal ecosystems. Each species of living organisms e.g. different fisheries, coral reefs, mangroves etc. have their different and unique contributions in the existence and functioning of the ecosystem. Ironically, these natural capitals of many marine and coastal ecosystems have been degraded, impacting upon the provision of services and livelihoods. About 20% of the world's coral reefs have been lost and another 20% degraded (Wilkinson 2008). Mangroves have been reduced to 30-50% of their historical cover and it is estimated that 29% of sea grass habitats have disappeared since the late eighteenth hundreds (Nellemann, Corcoran, Duarte, Valdes, De Young, Fonseca and Grimsditch (eds), (2009). This call for the need for sustainable use of biodiversity, with due consideration or respect to ecological parameters so as not to over use or exploit them, thereby destabilizing the entire system. Over population of human species put pressure on certain species of organism and even the environment. Also, some agricultural practices and the rapid urbanization of coastal areas are all major land based factors that cause higher levels of pollution in our seas. Hence an ecosystem management approach is necessary in restoration of biodiversity and renewable resources, and proper management of resource extraction.

It could also be done through food security from the blue economy perspective because it is very closely related to the sustainable use of biodiversity mainly where it pertains to the exploitation of wild fisheries. For example, in fisheries, some of the renowned "Sunken Billions" (FAO/IBRD, 2009), could be restored providing the basis for productive, efficient, sustainable fisheries and enhanced food security. The scientific determination and designation of appropriate Marine Ports

Authority (MPAs) can play a key role in this regard reconstituting biodiversity, ecosystem services and general resilience to other system shocks.

The role of the Educationist

Education is the process of facilitating learning, or acquisition of knowledge, skill, value, beliefs and habits. It means the development of a person to prepare him to adopt the best approach to a problem at any given time. It can be defined as adjustment ability to a changing situation and environment. According to Cavalevu (1979) in Agbo (2014), it means the upgrading of a man's ability to choose the best alternative available in any circumstance he faces. As one of the fundamental elements of the society or any community, it interacts with other elements within the society to bring about development and survival of man. When problems are assessed and needs identified, they could be addressed through national educational policies. Educational methods needed to enhance the sustainability of the blue economy, include teaching, training, workshops, seminars and directed research. All educational activities take place under the guidance of educators or educationists. Since education involves transfer of knowledge to enhance development, the Educationists at all levels therefore are stakeholders in the transfer of the requisite knowledge for the proper harnessing and sustainable development of the Blue Economy.

John Nasasira, Minister of ICT Republic of Uganda in an interview with New Times Rwanda pointed out that confronting the destruction of natural resources calls for professionalism, which he said will base on sustainable programmes to resource management. The strategy to be utilized by the educationist should be the training and re-training of all the different human resources.

The principles and need for conservation for sustainability that will ensure that economic development of the oceans and contribute to true prosperity and resilience in the now and in future proposed by the World Wildlife Fond (WWF) should be adopted and relayed to the general masses by the educationist. This is because people especially the rural poor have the mentality of "immediate" need satisfaction i.e. "give us this day our daily bread" without taking cognizance of tomorrow. The four cardinal points proposed by WWF include: cooperation amongst stakeholders and partners; delivering results by being effective and change agents for the conservation and sustainable management of the resources; influence regional policy by aligning with WWF as diligent watch dog that monitor how governments manage our common resource; and regional networking by forming a strong network in the region and making their presence felt in every meeting in the region and the surrounding countries.

Secondly, the educationist should mount seminars and workshops on skill acquisition through extension services. Furthermore, they should conduct basic researches and disseminate the correct information and knowledge acquired through well researched endeavours. The masses through the efforts of the educationists should be educated on the need for preservation of sport fish and wild life. They have to be educated on the global practices and existence of international agreements that have effect on the preservation of some species. For instance, due to ignorance, most stakeholders in water resources especially the rural masses, do not know that most species are protected absolutely in certain season, places and up to certain quota; some don't know where to get permit and that permit may be free or cost small amount, so they are at times over exploited by some so called

resources without permission is a serious offence. It is the job of the educationists to enlighten the masses on their rights and laws regarding proper utilization of water resources for sustainability. There is need for them to be taught about how to acquire or protect habitat, learn about other species or various species inhabiting the water environment; understand sets of regulations regarding how to harvest surplus stock of some species as well as protect some diminishing stock. This is achieved through the use of effective management system.

The educationist can help to conserve and sustain water resources through advocacy – bring to the knowledge of government and other policy makers the enormous wealth in the waters; bring to their knowledge some research works and findings on best practices for conserving these resources for sustainable development; they need to know how to collect and regulate the revenues gotten from water resources which can be used partly again to conserve the resources.

Each sovereign country is responsible for its own resources and sustainable development. This national responsibility and importance of national policies and development strategies should not therefore be downplayed. The principle of common but differentiated responsibilities, however, still applies. Indeed the need for structured international cooperation underpins all aspects of the Blue Economy. Whether it be with regard to updating and advancing governance mechanisms to ensure the sustainable development of waters beyond national jurisdiction (e.g. maritime security, sustainable fisheries, oil and mineral extraction) or assistance in enabling the effective management and utilization of national Exclusive Economic Zones (EEZs) (e.g. technology transfer, technical assistance, marine spatial planning, capacity building, finance to support national marine spatial planning and effective monitoring, control and surveillance) A key component of international

cooperation for the Blue Economy approach is Educational Research and Training.

A science-based approach is essential to the development of the Blue Economy; beginning with the initial assessment and critically the valuation of the blue capital at our disposal. This will provide a basis for informed decision-making and adaptive management. This major undertaken must be addressed and continually refined and upgraded in line with changing circumstances, evolving technologies and our increasing understanding; otherwise the Blue Economy approach will come to nothing. This underlines the importance of technical assistance, technology transfer through proper education and capacity building (train the trainer approach) to the pursuit of sustainable development.

Besides that, the effect of pollution and anthropogenic activities emanating from both the numerous coasts and coastlands, in particular, the activities of the Niger Delta Militants, the Avengers and other oil pipe line vandals are becoming more and more complex. The dumping of toxic wastes such as the KOKO toxic wastes of 1997 and a repeat at same site in February 2017 calls for urgent educational orientation and re-orientation to avert future occurrence. In 2016 alone the number of pipeline vandalization in Nigeria reached astronomic level and only the educationist could from the grassroots (primary levels) positively change the mindset of such vandals through systematic impartation of knowledge and awareness creation. Of recent the training of Niger Delta Militants in aquaculture and other trades have in no small measure curbed the activities of the restless youth turned gainfully employed/engaged youths.

The curriculum should be repositioned by enhancing its content with update of global practices regarding the use of water resources. The young minds at primary level up to tertiary level should be acquainted with the resources in the water and how they can be sustainably utilized. The different stakeholders that manage different sectors like fishing, tourism, submarine, aquaculture etc in the blue economy

should be properly trained by the professionals in the science of fishing, tourism, submarine, aquaculture and sustainability. Awareness programme on the management and utilization of water resources should be organized for the rural dwellers that draw their main economy from the ocean.

Conclusion

The potentials of the coastal and marine ecosystems (Blue Economy) though enormous as stated above are under serious pressure due to over-exploitation, over exploration and pollution activities hence the inevitable role of the educationist in training and re-training of the populace on the vast potentials, different strategies for conservation and sustainability of the aquatic resources for posterity. By so doing the Chinese adage “*give a man a fish and you feed him for a day; teach a man to fish and you feed him for a lifetime*” will be actualized.

Recommendations

- There should be awareness campaign on conservation and sustainable management and utilization of Blue Economy.
- The Train-the-Trainers Approach should be adopted from time to time to give up-to-date information on the potentials, conservation and sustainability of the Blue Economy.
- Constant monitoring and evaluation of the Blue Economy by relevant bodies should be carried out intermittently.

References

- Food and Agricultural Organisation (FAO) (2010). *The State of World Fisheries and Aquaculture*. Rome: FAO. <http://www.fao.org/3/a-i1820e.pdf>
- FAO (2012). *The State of World Fisheries and Aquaculture*. Rome: FAO. <http://www.fao.org/3/a-i2727e.pdf>
- FAO/ The International Bank for Reconstruction and Development (IBRD) (2009) *The Sunken Billions – The economic justification for fisheries*

r e f o r m
<https://siteresources.worldbank.org/EXT/ARD/Resources/3366811224775570533/SunkenBillionsFinal.pdf>

- Global Ocean Commission (GOC) (2008). *Policy Brief on Fisheries and Aquaculture*. Global Oceans Conference. Organized by the Global Forum on Oceans, Coasts, and Islands and Hosted by the Government of Vietnam, Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development with principal funding from the Global Environment Facility.
- Global Ocean Partnership (GPO) (2013). <http://www.globalpartnershipforoceans.org/>
- Agbo, Nats (2014). *The Role of Functional Education in Nation-Building*. Being the text of a key note address at a maiden edition of the Annual National Conference Organised by the School of General Studies, Benue Polytechnic, Ugbokolo, Benue State, Wednesday 25, 2014.
- International Energy Agency (IEA) (2010). *World Energy Outlook 2010*. <http://www.worldenergyoutlook.org/media/weo2010.pdf>
- International Fish and FIFFO (2013). *Linkage between farmed fish and wild fish - fishmeal & fish oil as feed ingredients in the context of sustainable aquaculture*. Jonathan Shepherd, Director General, International Fishmeal & Fish Oil Organization, OECD Conference Paris 15th–16th April 2010.
- International Geosphere-Biosphere Programme (IGBP). *Intergovernmental Oceanographic Convention (IOC), Scientific Committee on Oceanic Research SCOR (2013). Ocean Acidification Summary for Policymakers – Third Symposium on the Ocean in a High-CO₂ World*. International Geosphere-Biosphere Programme, Stockholm, Sweden.

- IOC/UNESCO, IMO, FAO, UNDP.(2011). A Blueprint for Ocean Sustainability, Paris. http://www.unesco.org/fileadmin/MULTIMEDIA/HQ/SC/pdf/interagency_blue_paper_ocean_rioPlus20.pdf
- HMSO (1994). The University of Reading (ECIFM). Definitions of Sustainability- <http://www.ecifm.rdg.ac.uk/definitions.htm>
- Nellemann, C., Corcoran, E., Duarte, C. M., Valdés, L., De Young, C., Fonseca, L.&Grimsditch, G. (Eds).** (2009): Blue Carbon. The Role of Healthy Oceans in Binding Carbon.A Rapid Response Assessment. . GRID - Arendal. www.grida.no Printed by Birkeland Trykkeri AS, Norway
- Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) (2012).The Future of the exploring Ocean Economy the prospects for emerging ocean industries to 2030. <https://www.oecd.org/futures/Future%20of%20the%20Ocean%20Economy%20Project%20Proposal>
- Poseidon Aquatic Resource Management (PARM) (2004). Assessment of the sustainability of industrial fisheries producing fishmeal and fish oil. Ltd and the University of Newcastle-Upon-Tyne.
- Sherman, K, Aquarone M.C. & Adams, S. (eds) (2010).Sustainable the World's Large Marine Ecosystems. 2009 © International Union for Conservation of Nature and Natural Resources (IUCN) Printed in China
- United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD) (2012). Review of Maritime transport 2012.Report by UNCTAD Secretariat, United Nations, New York and Geneva http://unctad.org/en/PublicationsLibrary/rmt2012_en.
- United Nations Economic Commission for Africa (UNECA) (2015). The Africa's Blue Economy: A Policy Handbook. Printed in Addis Ababa
- United Nations Environmental Protection (UNEP) (2013). Green Economy Definition. <http://www.unep.org/greeneconomy/AboutGEI/>
- United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) (2015). Blue Economy: Sharing Success Stories to Inspire Change. www.unep.org/greeneconomy. UNEP Regional Seas Report and Studies No. 195.
- UNEP, FAO, IMO, UNDP, IUCN, GRID-Arendal (2012).Green Economy in a Blue World. Published by United Nations Environmental Programme (UNEP) 2012.
- United Nations World Tourism Organization (UNWATO) (2013).Tourism highlights 2013 edition. <http://www.e-unwto.org/doi/pdf/10.18111/9789284415427>
- Wilkinson, C. (2008).Status of Coastal reefs of the world 2008.Global Coral Reef Monitoring Network (GCRMN). http://www.icriforum.org/sites/default/files/GCRMN_Status_Coral_Reefs_2008.